

Quantitative gravimetric estimation :

Under the above mentioned conditions of pH, reagent concentration and temperature gravimetric estimations of different quantities of Au(III) were done. The conversion factor for complex to metal is 0.3376.

Effect of foreign ions :

There was no interference by the addition of different quantities of foreign ions (Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , CH_3COO^- , SO_4^{2-} , Cd^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Hg^{+2}) on the precipitation of Au(III) done in suitable conditions.

There are certain cations like Fe(III), Cu(II), Pt(IV) which interfered in the estimation of Au(III).

In the light of above facts reagent DEAPG may be recommended as a promising gravimetric reagent for gold(III).

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Paper and Cellulose Thin Layer Chromatography of Toxic Cations

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CLEAR separations of toxic cations¹⁻⁵ :—Ce(IV), Ni(II), Cu(II), Bi(III), Hg(II), Tl(I), Pb(II), Be(II) and As(V) were achieved by ascending paper and cellulose thin layer chromatography in solvents: (1) Ethyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : methyl ethyl ketone : chloroform : 12N. HCl (25 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 10); (2) Ethyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : chloroform : methyl ethyl ketone : 12N. HCl (20 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 15) and (3) Isopropyl alcohol : isoamyl alcohol : acetone : chloroform : 12N. HCl (25 : 5 : 30 : 30 : 10). The order of R_f values is : Hg > As > Bi > Cu > Pb > Ni > Ce > Be, Tl. The differential mobility and separation of cations is based on differential solubilization of their chlorocomplexes in these polar solvents.

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Maleianilic Acids as Derivatives for Characterization of Aromatic Primary Amines and Their Paper Chromatographic Detection and Separation

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AROMATIC primary amines were characterized in qualitative analysis by formation of corresponding maleianilic acids as derivatives. The maleianilic acids were obtained in pure state and in good yield and have sharp melting points. The corresponding maleianilic acids were detected and separated using paper chromatography. The coloured spots were clearly visible while rest were visualized in iodine vapours.

Subba Rao characterized some aromatic primary amines as a derivative of corresponding phthalanilic

acids¹. The present communication reports the preparation of fifteen maleianilic acids namely different hydroxy, methyl, chloro, bromo, nitro, naphthylmethyl, carboxy and sulpho maleianilic acids and their characterization by melting points, elemental analysis and ir studies. The paper chromatographic technique is applied for the detection and separation of maleianilic acids. The isomers can be resolved very successfully in acetone.

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Studies on the Humus Complexes in the Soils of Doon Valley under Sal (*Shorea robusta*)

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ON account of its significant role in the maintenance of soil fertility, the chemical investigation of humic acid has attached a great deal of importance in the recent past. Forsyth¹ and Kumada² found less humified materials containing a relatively greater amounts of $-OCH_3$ groups, which gradually decrease with the advance of humification, whereas Kosaka and Honda³ observed an increase in the values of carbon contents with the progress of humification. However, the chemistry of humus complexes in the soils of tropical forests has been little studied in spite of their extensive ecological significance⁴ and influence on forest growth⁵. The present study was, therefore, taken up in the humic-acid fractions of Doon Valley soils which are under sal (*Shorea robusta*) forests, so that they can be characterised on the basis of their elementary composition, exchange capacity and methoxyl group content for various fertility evaluation purposes.

Experimental

The present investigation has been confined to twelve soil samples collected from the surface and sub-surface horizons of the profiles exposed (two each) in the Asarori, Jhajra and Lacchiwala ranges of Dehra Dun (East and West) Forest Divisions which represent typical conditions of natural sal forests of Doon Valley. The general properties of the soils and the area have been described elsewhere^{6,7} and given in condensed from (Table 1).

The humic acid fractions from the soils were extracted with sodium pyrophosphatesodium hydroxide solutions following the rapid method of Kononova and Belchikova⁸ as described earlier⁴. The purified samples of humic acids were subjected to methylation with 10% KOH and 20 ml of dimethyl sulphate solutions and precipitated with dil. H_2SO_4 . The precipitates free from sulphates and after complete methylation were used for nitrogen CEC and methoxy group determinations. Carbon and nitrogen in the humic acids samples were determined by the conventional methods and the cation exchange capacity as $BaSO_4$ after leaching the samples with 0.5 N $BaCl_2$. For determining the methoxyl content (per cent of ash free sample) a portion of the sample (0.2 g) was heated with 5 ml of HI and its steam carrying the CH_3I , absorbed in alcoholic solution of $AgNO_3$ to obtain AgI which was filtered, thoroughly washed, dried and weighed.

Results and Discussion

It can be seen from the Table 2 that the carbon content of the humic acid fractions varies from 52.8 to 62.2 per cent with relatively higher amount in the samples from Asarori (Profile I & II) as compared to Jhajra (Profile III & IV) and Lacchiwala (Profile V & VI). Within the profile its content is more in the case of surface horizon than sub-surface. The content of nitrogen, however, show somewhat reverse order being relatively low in the former as compared to latter ones. Consequently the C/N ratio of the humic fractions is higher in the case of former (upto 11.84) in comparison to latter where it is as low as 7.86 (Profile VI). The CEC which is somewhat characteristic of all the humic acids has decreased markedly on methylation in all the cases but this decrease in the exchange capacity is not proportional to the increase in the methoxyl content which may be due to some blocking of the groups responsible for the exchange phenomena of humic acids, as a result of methylation. Half of the loss in CEC (Av. loss 12.45 per cent) and in nitrogen (Av. loss 13.65 per cent) can be accounted for the increase in weight of the molecules arising from the addition of methoxyl group. Analytical values show that the major portion of the humic nitrogen has remained as an inseparable part of the humic acids even after repeated methylation to a constant methoxyl content^{10,11,12}. The loss of nitrogen on methylation, further proves that nitrogen is a constituent of the humic molecule¹. It appears that during the process of humus formation and progress in humification there has been a gradual depletion of methoxyl groups and subsequent increase in the acid groups.

On comparing humic acids between themselves the samples from Profiles I & II are found relatively more humified and condensed than Profiles III & IV and Profiles V & VI on account of relatively higher